

STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF CONTACT MISTUNING ON THE FLUTTER OF INTERLOCKED TURBINE BLADES USING A CONCEPTUAL MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Turbine rows with interlocked blades show complex and often poorly understood dynamics. In many cases they show significant blade-to-blade variability, including some features that are inconsistent with the typical behavior of (non-interlocked) mistuned bladed rows.

In this article a simplified conceptual model has been formulated in order to explain the dynamics of interlocked rows. Both the influence of conventional mistuning, introduced as a variability on the natural frequencies of the isolated blades, and of contact mistuning, associated to the variability of the interference between shrouds have been studied. The results of the article show a behavior which is qualitatively different from the usual in mistuned rows, involving complex assembly modes with large differences in the mode-shapes of the individual blades. This leads to complicated FRF functions with multiple, closely packed peaks.

NOMENCLATURE

Δ Displacement for the bending motion
 μ Real modal mass fraction

θ Rotation angle for the torsion mode
 ξ Critical damping ratio
 δ Modal amplitude
DOF Degree of freedom
FEM Finite Element Method
CFD Computational Fluid Dynamics
EO Engine Order
J Torsional moent of inertia of the blade
j Imaginary unit
 K_C Contact stiffness between blade shrouds
FRF Frequency response function
 d Half-width of the shroud
 K_F Bending stiffness of the blade
 K_S Shroud stiffness
 K_T Torsional stiffness of the blade
M Blade Mass
 M_{mod} Modal mass
N Total number of blades in the row
ND Nodal Diameter
Q Dynamic amplification factor
TW Traveling Wave

- * Complex conjugate
- Vector

Sub-scripts

- i Blade index

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to reduce weight and improve efficiency, current trends for the design of aeronautical turbines involve thin and slender rotor blades. Unfortunately, this leads to significant risks in terms of vibration, including aeroelastic phenomena such as flutter. A widespread solution to reduce these dynamic issues is the use of interlocked blades, where the blades are assembled with a pre-twist that ensures tight contact between the shrouds of adjacent blades. This increases the natural frequency of the assembly modes and reduces the risk of flutter and similar phenomena.

Nevertheless, there are noticeable drawbacks to this solution. On one hand, the dynamic behavior of the configuration is complicated and difficult to predict; both the modal frequencies and shapes are very dependent on the characteristics of the contacts between the shrouds [1]. On the other hand, and despite the sharp increase in the natural frequency, flutter is still a risk in interlocked turbine blades [2, 3, 4].

Another complication is the very significant scatter in the blade-to-blade readings of interlocked rows [5, 6]. The common understanding of this phenomenon relies on the sensitivity of the modal characteristics to the details of the inter-shroud contacts. Due to manufacturing tolerances, or variations in the positioning of the blades, there is significant scatter in the actual contacts between the shrouds in a real row, leading to the reported scatter on the dynamic characteristics of the blades.

This paper aims to explain the basics of this dynamic scatter in interlocked blades and its impact on the flutter of interlocked blade rows. This conceptual study will be based on an advanced version of the simplified model that we presented in [7], which provided a good explanation for the flutter mechanism in interlocked blades.

2 SIMPLIFIED INTERLOCK MODEL

An sketch highlighting the main parameters of the model may be found in Figure 1. The main hypotheses behind the model for interlock dynamics presented in [7] were:

1. Two degrees of freedom per blade:
 - (a) A torsion mode (torsional inertia J , torsional stiffness K_T). The torsion center is in the middle of the shroud, which has a width $2d$.
 - (b) An edge-wise bending mode (mass M , stiffness K_F)
2. The disk is considered infinitely stiff.

FIGURE 1. MODEL SKETCH: UPDATE Kc!!

3. The shrouds remain in contact. This imposes a kinematic constraint between the motions of adjacent blades. Nevertheless, the shrouds themselves have a finite stiffness K_S .
4. No damping for either mode.

The model retained most of the key features of the dynamics of interlocked turbine blades, including:

- Modal frequencies increase very significantly with the nodal diameter and saturate at high values of the ND .
- Mode-shapes change very obviously with the ND , beginning as fundamentally edge-wise flexion modes and eventually turning into torsion modes.
- There is a range of ND s where the modes are clearly complex modes which combine bending and torsion. These complex modes are prone to flutter.

In this work, the formulation is nearly identical, but individual variations of the blade properties (K_F , K_T , etc.) are retained, and thus are defined on a per-blade basis (e. g. K_{Ti} referring to the torsional stiffness of the blade i). Furthermore, the 'shroud stiffness' K_S is replaced by a 'contact stiffness' K_C . Even though K_S was considered a property of the shroud of each individual blade in the previous work, in this paper the equivalent parameter is K_C , with K_{Ci}^- referring to the stiffness related to the contact between the shrouds of the blades $i-1$ and i , and K_{Ci}^+ to the contact between the blades i and $i+1$. This means that $K_{Ci}^+ = K_{Ci+1}^-$. Of course, in a tuned case where all the properties are identical among the blades both variables would be equivalent. Taking this into account, and proceeding just like in the previous paper, the main equations for the model become:

$$M_i \frac{d^2 \Delta_i}{dt^2} + (K_{Fi} + K_{Ci}^+ + K_{Ci}^-) \Delta_i - K_{Ci}^+ \Delta_{i-1} - K_{Ci}^- \Delta_{i+1} + (K_{ci}^+ - K_{ci}^-) d_i \theta_i + K_{ci}^+ d \theta_{i-1} + K_{ci}^- d \theta_{i+1} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$J_i \frac{d^2 \theta_i}{dt^2} + (K_{Ti} + K_{ci}^+ d^2 + K_{ci}^- d^2) \theta_i + K_{ci}^+ d^2 \theta_{i-1} + K_{ci}^- d^2 \theta_{i+1} + (K_{ci}^+ - K_{ci}^-) d \Delta_i + K_{ci}^+ d \Delta_{i-1} + K_{ci}^- d \Delta_{i+1} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Overall, for a rotor with N blades there are $2N$ equations, describing 2 degrees of freedom per blade.

As discussed in the previous paper [7], in a tuned case (i.e., all sectors have identical properties) it is possible to find traveling wave solutions with ND nodal diameters following a pattern $e^{j(\omega t + \frac{2\pi i ND}{N})}$. Under these circumstances, it is trivial to determine the modal frequencies and shapes as a function of the nodal diameter. Resuming the main conclusions from [7], in a typical case, the frequency increases very significantly with the nodal diameter, as shown in Figure 2. On the other hand, the mode-shape also depends strongly on the nodal diameter. The modes are complex and involve both a bending component (Δ) and a torsional component (θ), which appear out-of-phase. If we define the bending mass factor μ as:

$$\mu = \frac{M\Delta^2}{M\Delta^2 + J\theta^2} \quad (3)$$

It is possible to study how the modal characteristics evolve with the nodal diameter. As shown in 2, the frequency increases significantly with the nodal diameter, moving from the edge-wise frequency until reaching the pure torsion value. Unsurprisingly, the modes are pure bending modes for $ND = 0$, but the torsion component increases steadily until becoming pure torsion modes for high ND . This frequency increase is clearly tied to the strong coupling in the movement of the adjacent blades.

Following the formulation that was also discussed in [7], it is possible to include the effect of the unsteady aerodynamics through aerodynamic influence matrices. This approach led to the prediction of flutter instabilities in a range of ND , coincident with markedly complex normal modes (i.e., with comparable flexion and torsion components). This behavior is consistent with results from detailed CFD simulations based on 3D FEM models, as can be seen in Figure 3.

An aspect of the problem that was not addressed in [7] is synchronous response. Assuming a forcing following a

FIGURE 2. Evolution of the modal characteristics with the nodal diameter

FIGURE 3. Aerodynamic damping for the tuned model

traveling-wave pattern and constant total damping for all vibration modes (corresponding to a dynamic amplification factor Q), the problem can be easily described using basic vibration theory. Each vibration mode for the assembly follows a traveling wave pattern and may only be excited by a forcing with a compatible traveling wave pattern. The forced response function, as shown in Figure 4, simply follows the canonical form for single degree-of-freedom vibration problems, with the resonance frequency coincident with the modal frequency for the adequate ND index.

These results summarize the basics of the behavior of the tuned model as described in [7]. In the paper, it was shown

FIGURE 4. Forced Response Frequency for the tuned model

that by adjusting the constants of the model it is possible to reproduce with reasonable accuracy the dynamics of interlocked blades, as determined through detailed FEM + CFD simulations; this strongly suggests that the simplified model provides a good approximation of the basics of the physics. Nevertheless, the work in [7] only considered an ideal tuned case and did not contemplate the variability of the interlocked blades. The aim of this article is to expand the model to consider these mistuning effects, and compare results with the typical behavior of a non-interlocked bladed disk.

3 EFFECT OF THE SHROUD INTERFERENCE ON MODAL CHARACTERISTICS

Determining the modal characteristics of interlocked blades, even in a tuned case, is not trivial; it is difficult to match accurately experimental results. A key part of the problem is to characterize the contact between blades; interlocked blades are assembled with a pre-twist that induces a degree of interference between the shrouds of the blade, and it has a large impact on their modal characteristics [1]. Furthermore, it can be argued that linear modes are not very representative of interlock dynamics because the interaction between the shrouds (both normal contact and friction) is strongly non-linear, which makes it difficult to relate empirical vibration data with linear modes.

For the purpose of this article we will consider the following approach to determine the vibration modes:

- Perform a non-linear static simulation considering the potential contact between shrouds. The pre-twist between the blades needs to be accounted for. The most relevant result of this simulation is the part of the nominal contact face that

FIGURE 5. Contact stress distribution for the test case. The surface in grey is not actually in contact

is actually in contact for a given operation condition.

- Impose 'tied' boundary conditions in the nodes that were determined 'in contact' thanks to the previous simulation.
- Obtain the linear modes associated to the previous steady state (i.e., considering the pre-stress state and the contact surface as determined from the static analysis).

This approach is similar, but not fully consistent, with a formal linearization of the problem; the variation of the contact surface during the vibration cycle is not retained, not even in a linearized form.

Typically, interlocked blades are manufactured with tight tolerances; in particular, the surfaces directly related to the contact between shrouds are machined with very strict requirements. Nevertheless, it is essentially impossible to control the assembly process to the same degree. Furthermore, experience suggests that there are small changes in the positioning of the blades during operation, leading to non-negligible variability in the interference of the different contacts between shrouds. For the purpose of this section, we will assume that the most relevant source of variability between blades corresponds to the interference, at least regarding the contacts between the shrouds.

Let us consider a representative case corresponding to an interlocked low pressure turbine blade. There are 94 blades in the row. Considering nominal operation conditions and the intended pre-twist value, we can see contact results from a FEM analysis in Figure 5. No contact is predicted for the area in grey; colored regions indicate the contact stress level. It can be seen that a significant (around 50%) fraction of the nominal contact face is predicted to actually be in contact. Modal frequencies, in Figure 6, behave as usual in interlocked blades, following the qualitative description in section 2.

The effect of changing the interference value from the design intent is shown in Figures 7 and 8. The maximum and minimum values for the interference have been estimated from experimental data. The variable interference has been induced by modifying the pre-twist angle of the blades. In Figure 7, it can be seen that the predicted contact face changes significantly with the interference value, with lower interference leading to a

FIGURE 6. FEM Modal Frequency and bending factor μ for the test case

FIGURE 8. Modal frequencies for different interference values

FIGURE 7. Contact area for different interference values. Left: nominal -0.4 mm. Right: Nominal +0.45 mm

reduction in the contact area and the related stress. This leads to an effective reduction in the stiffness of the model, and the consequent reduction in the blade natural frequencies, as can be seen in Figure 8. For intermediate values of the nodal diameter (ND around 12-18), the frequencies may change as much as 5%.

In order to account for this effect inside the simplified model, it has been assimilated to a variation in the K_C value for the different contacts between the shroud DOFs of the model. For each interference value, the K_C constant in the simplified model has been adjusted in order to match the frequency curve as obtained from the FEM. In Figure 9 it can be seen that the best fit of K_C depends strongly with the interference, with changes larger than $\pm 25\%$ for extreme values of the interference.

4 IMPACT OF MISTUNING ON INTERLOCKS CONSIDERING THE SIMPLIFIED MODEL

The impact of geometric variability and similar sources of imperfection in cyclic bladed disks has been widely studied. In most circumstances it has been analyzed using perturbation methods such as FMM [8] or the very similar AMM [9]. Some of the best known conclusions that can be obtained with such

FIGURE 9. Variation of K_C with the interference value

approaches are:

- Mistuning can be characterized by considering the frequency variation of the blade-alone modes of the individual blades.
- Mistuned assembly modes are no longer traveling waves. The mode-shape for each blade follows approximately the blade-alone mode-shape, but the amplitude varies strongly from blade to blade.

These basic conclusions do not necessarily apply to realistic rows of interlocked blades.

In the following analysis, mistuning has been included in

FIGURE 10. Randomly generated mistuning patterns

FIGURE 11. Aeroelastic eigenvalue maps

our conceptual model in two different ways:

- A small, random variation in the flexion and torsion stiffness constants (K_F , K_T) of the different blades. A Gaussian distribution has been assumed, with a standard deviation of 2% of the average value (which is roughly equivalent to 1% of frequency scatter). This is reasonably representative of mistuning associated to manufacturing tolerances and similar sources in cantilevered turbine blades.
- A larger variation in the contact stiffness K_C between the different pairs of blades. Following the results obtained in Section 3, a Gaussian distribution with a standard deviation of 10% of the average value is assumed.

Following these rules two random mistuning patterns have been generated (Figure 10): pattern A, affecting only K_F and K_T (shown as mistuning in the blade-alone frequency), and pattern B, affecting K_C .

By introducing mistuning patterns into the model (Eq. 1 and 2), including the aerodynamic terms, it is possible to obtain the aeroelastic eigenvalues and eigenmodes for the mistuned system. The eigenvalue maps for the tuned case, the mistuned case including pattern A, the mistuning case including pattern B and the case including both are depicted in Figure 11.

The impact of pattern A on the eigenvalues is very small. This is not surprising; classical mistuning theory indicates that mistuning effectiveness decreases in cases with strong coupling between blades, which corresponds to large differences in the frequencies of the individual traveling waves. On the other hand, pattern B has a much stronger impact, with noticeable stabilization of the flutter modes. It must be taken into account that, in practice, pattern B corresponds to stronger mistuning than pattern A; as discussed in section 3, the variability in the contact

interference can induce differences in frequency as large as 5%. This stronger mistuning is able to overcome the modal separation due to the coupling between modes and achieve effective traveling wave mixing.

Analyzing the mode-shapes leads to similar conclusions. The aeroelastic mode closest to the tuned *ND-18* mode for pattern A is depicted in Figure 12, while the same for pattern B is depicted in Figure 13. The mode has been chosen for being one of the most unstable modes for the tuned case. The upper graph shows the amplitude of the flexion DOF for each blade, while the lower graph shows its azimuthal Fourier transform. The case with pattern A shows fairly small variations in amplitude between the different blades, indicating that the vibration mode remains essentially a pure traveling wave. Therefore, the Fourier transform is very clearly dominated by the *ND-18* traveling wave pattern. On the other hand, the results for pattern B show large variations in the amplitude for each blade, and the Fourier transform indicates important contributions from multiple traveling waves.

In Figure 14 the bending mass fraction μ (Equation 3) for each blade is shown. In practice, this parameter indicates the effective mode-shape that each blade is experimenting. For the case with mistuning pattern A the parameter shows small variations between the blades, around 5%, indicating that all of them are vibrating essentially with the same mode-shape; this is consistent with the most usual behavior in mistuned bladed-disks. On the other hand, this is not true for the case with mistuning pattern B. In this case each blade has very distinctly different mode-shapes (bending parameters changing as much as 70%). The practical implications are very interesting; the usual approaches for the measurements of vibrations inside an engine (strain-gauges, BTT) rely strongly on an assumption that the

FIGURE 12. Representative aeroelastic mistuned mode (pattern A)

FIGURE 14. Bending parameter μ for the representative mode. Up: pattern A. Bottom: pattern B

FIGURE 13. Representative aeroelastic mistuned mode (pattern B)

mode-shape of each blade is known in advance (and in the vast majority of cases, the same for all blades in the row). The behavior of the model strongly suggests that mode-shapes will change from blade to blade and will be very difficult to predict accurately in advance, greatly complicating the post-processing of vibration tests.

Table 1 resumes the results from a Monte Carlo analysis involving 1000 randomly generated mistuning patterns, affecting either the blade stiffness (K_F , K_T), the contact stiffness K_C or both. The results refer to the damping for the most unstable mode for each random row. As expected, the impact of the mistuning on the blade stiffness is minimal, but the effect of the contact

	Tuned	Blade Mist.	Contact Mist.	Both
Average	-0.086%	-0.084%	-0.066%	-0.063%
STD		0.0005%	0.0030%	0.0051%

TABLE 1. Damping results from a Monte Carlo analysis

stiffness is non-negligible. Nevertheless, even the contact mistuning is unable to fully stabilize flutter, at least in the majority of the cases.

Using the model it is also possible to study synchronous response. For this exercise, we assumed a constant dynamic amplification factor $Q = 50$ for all modes. Then, we excited the simplified model of the row considering a forcing in the K_F DOF following an $EO = 10$ pattern. The Forced Response Functions (FRFs) for a few representative DOF, both bending and torsion, can be seen in Figures 15 (for a row including mistuning pattern A) and 16 (mistuning pattern B). The figures also include the response of the tuned system (solid black line) and the envelope of the FRFs of all the DOF of the row (dashed line).

Results for the row with mistuning pattern A show a behavior consistent with weakly mistuned rows. The shape of the FRFs is generally consistent with classical single DOF theory, with some minor noise. The envelope shows only a small amplification factor comparing with the tuned case, less than 5%.

Results for the row with contact mistuning (pattern B) are much more interesting. As can be seen in Figure 16, the response of the individual DOF follow complex FRFs with clear qualitative differences from the tuned case and even between the separate blades. Some curves show responses with multiple peaks.

FIGURE 15. FRF considering mistuning pattern A

FIGURE 16. FRF considering mistuning pattern B

Furthermore, when comparing the FRFs for the torsion DOF with the corresponding FRF for the bending DOF for a given blade, it becomes apparent that they can show large qualitative differences (e.g. the bending DOF for blade 28 shows relatively low response with two clear peaks with roughly the same amplitude, whereas the torsion DOF has a comparatively much higher response with a clear single peak). This indicates that the ODS for the blades will change very significantly, both when comparing different blades in the row and when comparing different peaks in the response. Overall, the impact of mistuning is large, with amplification factors (considering the envelope) above 50%.

The reasons behind this behavior are complicated. Since the normal modes of the assembly are no longer traveling waves, the orthogonality with a traveling wave excitation does not apply and multiple assembly modes will be excited even by a pure traveling wave forcing. Furthermore, the modes involve different motions (given by the different bending parameter) for the blades in the row. If we add into the equation that the mistuned modes show different degrees of localization and that the assembly modes have relatively similar natural frequencies, we arrive at a very complex problem where it is very difficult to identify simplified rules for the behavior of the blades.

These results, obtained from a simple conceptual model, provide some insight into the dynamics of interlocked mistuned rows, and also hint at the difficulties for detailed analyses. In particular, the large changes in the mode-shape of the different blades when contact mistuning is added indicate clash with the hypotheses behind most common mistuning models (such as FMM [8]), making more complex approaches, such as [10],

mandatory.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The impact of mistuning on rows of interlocked turbine blades has been studied using a conceptual model. Two different sources of mistuning were considered: frequency mistuning (typical source in turbine blades) and contact mistuning (primarily associated to the interlock assembly).

Overall, and considering representative deviations between blades, contact mistuning appears by far the dominant phenomenon, both in flutter and forced response. Contact mistuning may induce effects that are not usual in mistuned bladed disks, such a major variability of the apparent motion of vibration for the different blades in the row. This introduces important difficulties to the analysis of mistuned interlocked rows, both from a theoretical point of view (since it make popular approaches such as FMM very inaccurate) and experimental (since the interpretation of measurement systems such as SGs or BTT becomes far from trivial).

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